

Chewing Lice of Black Partridge *Francolinusfrancolinus* Birds in Al-Diwaniyah Province/ Iraq

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Abstract.

This study was performed to detect the chewing lice infested black partridge *Francolinusfrancolinus* birds, for this aim 109 birds were collected from different areas in Al-Diwaniyah province during the period from August to December 2019. The results found 53 out of a totally 109 (48.62%) birds were infested with at least one chewing louse species and four species of chewing lice were reported: *Menopongallinae*, *Menacanthustramineus*, *Goniocotesgallinae* and *Lipeuruscaponis*. A significant difference was noted at ($P \leq 0.05$) between male and female of infested birds, also a significant difference at ($P \leq 0.05$) in infestation type, the single infestation rate was highest (26.60%) followed by double and triple infestation rates (11.92%) and (10.09%) respectively.

Keywords. Chewing Lice, Black Partridge, Al-Diwaniyah Province.

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INTRODUCTION

Birds were infected with various types of pathogens, such as parasites, bacteria and viruses, which makes them a major risk to humans and domestic animals, because they are an important food source in addition to their role in transmitting the infection to healthy birds (Derakhshanar, 2003), ectoparasites which permanent or temporary parasitism of birds cause histological changes in the skin, muscles, liver, spleen and lungs that leading to the death of infested birds, (Prelezov *et al.*, 2002)also it was intermediate hosts for some Cestodes and Nematodes (Permin, and Hansen,1998),lice that belong to Mallophaga which most distributed ectoparasites in birds, found in different parts of the bird's body such as the head, wings, chest and abdomen (Clayton *et al.*, 1999), feed on chewing feathers, dry skin and blood-sucking (Salifou *et al.*, 2008), and spend each life cycle on its host because it needs warmth and heat to survive (Hill, 2007).

Several studies have reported different species of chewing lice on several types of birds in Al-Diwaniya province, Al-Jubori (2010), who recorded *Menacanthustramineus*, *M. pallidullus*, *M. cornutus*, *Menopongallinae*, *Goniodesgigas* and *Gonicotesgallinae* parasitic on domestic chickens, Al-Shaibani (2015) found *Meleagrisgallopavo* infested with *Menacanthustramineus*, *Goniodesgigas*, *Gonoiocotesgallinae*, *Oxylipeurus*, Al-Aredhi and Al-Mayali (2019) reported *Menacanthustramineus*, *M. cornutus*, *M. eurysternus*, *Trinotonquerquedulae*, *Menopongallinae*, *Saemundssonaria lari*, *Columbicolacolumbae*, *Fulicoffula gallinule* and *Anaticolacrasssicorins* parasitic on migratory aquatic birds of Al-Delmaj marsh, the aim of study to isolate and identify chewing lice from *Francolinusfrancolinus* in Al-Diwaniya province/ Iraq.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

During the period from August to December 2019, 109black partridge *Francolinusfrancolinus* (51 males and 58 females) were collected from different areas in Al-Diwaniyah province and brought to the laboratory of parasites in biology department, faculty of Education, Al-Qadisiyah University, birds were classified by (Allouse 1960). The birds were examined by necked eye and also using a magnifying glass to manually isolate chewing lice from the feathers, preserved in ethanol alcohol 70%, placed in KOH 10%for 24 hours to clarify, then washed with distilled water and placed in Xaylol for 1-2 minutes and mounted on slides using a canada balsam, (Dik and Uslu, 2011), examined under a light microscope and identify based on Price *et al.* (2003).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Chi square test was used to statistically analyze the results at (P<0.05) (Al-Rawi, 1984).

RESULTS

Results of the current study showed that examined birds were infested with four species of chewing lice: *Menopongallinae*, *Menacanthustramineus*, *Goniocotesgallinae* and *Lipeuruscaponis* with infestation rate (48.62%) as show in table (1) and figures 1-4.

Table 1. Chewing lice species isolated from black partridge birds in Al-Diwaniya province.

Lice species	No. infested	Percentage
<i>Menopongallinae</i>	53	48.62
<i>Menacanthustramineus</i>	41	37.61
<i>Gonicotesgallinae</i>	33	30.72
<i>Lipeuruscaponis</i>	28	25.68

Table 2. Shows a Higher Infestation Rate Infemale Birds with Chewing Lice Compared to Males Birds

Table 2. Infestation Rate of Chewing Lice Species According to Gender

gender of birds	No. examined	No. infested	percentage
Male	51	19	37.25
Female	58	34	*58.62
Total	109	53	

*indicate a significant difference using Chi square test at (P <0.05).

It was also noted that the single infestation rate in one species of lice was highest (26.60%) followed by double infestation (11.92%) and triple infestation (10.09%) as table (3).

Table 3. Infestation Type of Chewing Lice in Examined Birds

Infestation type	No. infested	percentage
Single	29	*26.60
Double	13	11.92
Triple	11	10.09
Total	53	

*indicate a significant difference using Chi square test at (P <0.05).

DISCUSSION

Black partridge birds live in the form populations, feed on insects, larvae, ants, seeds, and buds and their presence affected by drought and server cold (Liao *et al*, 2007).

There are more than 5500 species of chewing lice have been described, and about 4000 of them are reported (Price *et al.*, 2003).

During the current study four species of chewing lice have been found on black partridge which were collected from different areas in Al-Diwaniya province and these species were: *Menopongallinae*, *Menacanthustramineus*, *Gonicotesgall*, *Lipeuruscaaponis* with infestation rate (48.62%), these results agreement with Khattak *et al.* (2012) in Pakistan who isolated five species of chewing lice were: *Menopongallinae*, *Gonicotes gall*, *Menacanthustramineus*, *Lipeuruscaaponis*, and *Generocolumbicola* from black partridge with infestation rate (84.4%), Difference in rates recorded maybe due to the difference in the number of birds examined, the study area and climatic conditions.

The results of study showed the highest infestation rate with chewing lice in females birds compared to males birds, this is similar to study done by Calnek *et al.* (1991) and Ciszewska *et al.* (1996), they showed significant differences in the infestation rates among genders and noted that females were more susceptible to infestation with chewing lice than males because of their long stay in the nests for incubation young birds makes them more susceptible to infestation compared males which spend most of their time flying to collect food.

The current study showed that infestation rate with one species of chewing lice was highest its agree with the results of Al-Jabouri (2010) and Mohammed (2014) where they reported that single infestation was more prevalent than the rest because of the living and environmental competition between parasites over the host.

REFERENCES

- [1] Allouse BA (1960). Birds of Iraq. *Baghdad: ArRabita Press* 1: 213. (In Arabic).
- [2] Al-Aredhi HS, Al-Mayali HM (2019). Chewing lice parasitic on migratory aquatic birds in Al-Delmaj marsh/Iraq. *Eurasian Journal of Biosciences* 13(1): 555-559.

- [3] Al-Jubori SA (2010). Endo and Ecto-Parasitic Infections in house breeding chicken *Gallus gallusdomesticus* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Al-Diwaniya City. Master thesis, College of Education, University of Al-Qadisiyah.
- [4] Al-Rawi KM (1984). Introduction to statistics. *Coll. Agri. Univ. Mosul*: 496. In Arabic.
- [5] Al-shabani HA (2015). Diagnostic and taxonomical study of Turkey (*Meleagrisgallopavo*) Parasites in AL-Qadisiya Province. Master thesis, College of Education, University of Al-Qadisiyah.
- [6] Calneck BW, Barness HJ, Bre AC, Reid WM, Yoder H (1991). Diseases of poultry, *9thed. Iow9 University Press- Ames, USA*: 723 – 778.
- [7] Ciszewska M, Peteryszak A; Bonczar Z, Duda M (1996). Mallophaga of pigeon (*Columba livia*) in Cracow. *Wild. Parasitol.*, 42(2): 42- 235.
- [8] Clayton DH, Lee PLM, Tompkins DM, Brodie ED (1999). Reciprocal natural selection on host-parasite phenotypes. *The American Naturalist* 154(3): 261-270.
- [9] Derakhshanar A, Radfar MH, Taefinasrabadi N (2003). A study on parasites of the digestive system and related lesions of pigeons in city of Kerman, Iran. *Pajouhesh-Va-Sazandegi* 16 (1): 37-41.
- [10] Dik B, Yamac EE, Uslu U (2011). Chewing lice Phthiraptera found in wild birds in Turkey. *Kafkas Univ Vet Fak Derg*, 175:787-794.
- [11] Hill, J.R. (2007). Purple Martin Update., 5(1):1-7.
- [12] Khattak RM, Ali S, Jahangir M, Nasir Khan M, Rasul A, Iqbal F (2012). Prevalence of Ectoparasites in wild and domesticated Grey (*Francolinuspondicerianus*) and Black Partridges (*Francolinusfranco-linus*) from Khyber Pakhtoonkhwa Province of Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Zoology* 44(5): 1239-1244.
- [13] Liao WB, Hu JC, Li C (2007). Habitat utilization during the pairing season by the common Hill Francolin *Arborophilatorqueola* in Baiposhan Natural Reserve, Sichuan, China. *Ornithological Science* 6(2): 87-94.
- [14] Mohammad ZA (2014). Ectoparasites and helminthes of some aquatic birds in Al-Sanaf Marsh, southern Thi-Qar province / Iraq. *PhD Thesis, Coll. Educ. Univ. Basrah*: 218.
- [15] Permin A, Hansen JW (1998). Epidemiology, diagnosis and control of poultry parasites FAO Animal Health Manuals 4. Rome: *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)*: 160.
- [16] Prelezov PN, Gundasheva DI, Groseva NI (2002). Haematological changes in chickens experimentally infected with biting lice (phthiraptera: Insecta). *Bulgarian J. Vet. Med.*, 5: 2938.
- [17] Price RD, Hellenthal RA, Palma RL, Johnson KP, Clayton DH (2003). The Chewing Lice: world checklist and biological overview. *Illinois Nat. Hist. Sur. Spec. Publ.*, 24: 54-61.
- [18] Salifou S, Natta YA, Odjo AM, Pangui LJ (2008). Arthropodes ectoparasites du dindon (*Meleagris gallopavo*) dans le nord-ouest du Bénin. *Revue d'élevage et de médecine vétérinaire des pays tropicaux* 61(3-4): 185-189.